

Value Chart.

This value chart uses binary base code to make algorithms out of the code.

The old positive and negative value chart.

The winner set values, the winner set hands. The perpetually locked values.

The 36th positive decimal place. The nothing hand, the auto-installation think value: . . .

The 35th positive decimal place. The 0th place winner, the something hand, the auto-invent think value. The: , ,

The 34th positive decimal place. The 1st place winners, the auto-complete value think hand.

The 33rd positive decimal place. The 2nd place winners, the auto-check value think hand.

The 32nd positive decimal place. The 3rd place winners, the auto-error-correct value think hand.

The finalist set values, the final hands. The locked values.

The 31st positive decimal place. The inner hidden final feature value think hand.

The 30th positive decimal place. The inner seen final feature value think hand.

The 29th positive decimal place. The hidden middle final feature value think hand.

The 28th positive decimal place. The seen middle final feature value think hand.

The 27th positive decimal place. The hidden outer final feature value think hand.

The 26th positive decimal place. The seen outer final feature value think hand.

The 25th positive decimal place. The last hidden final feature value think hand.

The scientific values.

The scientific annotated top value hands, the front pseudo-positive dimensional hands.

The pseudo-positive old 24th decimal place. The clone pseudo-negative year filters into perpetual-pseudo positive year reflects the clone pseudo-negative hour filters into perpetual pseudo-positive hour. Clone superior think filters into perpetual inferior guess. The <<<<^“?”| top space year hand and the <<<<^““?\ top time hour hand.

The pseudo-positive old 23rd decimal place. The pseudo-positive month reflects the pseudo-positive minute. Middle case superior think filters into inferior middle case guess. The <<<<^?”| top space month hand and the <<<<^““?\ top time minute hand.

The pseudo-positive old 22nd decimal place. The pseudo-positive day reflects the pseudo-positive second. The somewhat superior think filters into inferior somewhat guess. The <<<<^,?”| top space day hand and the <<<<^,““?\ top time second hand.

The scientific annotated outer value hands, the front pseudo-positive dimensional hands.

The pseudo-positive old 21st decimal place. The clone pseudo-negative year filters into perpetual-pseudo positive year reflects the clone pseudo-negative hour filters into perpetual pseudo-positive hour. Clone superior think filters into perpetual inferior guess. The <<<^“?”| upper space year hand and the <<<^“?”\ upper time hour hand. The pseudo-positive old 20th decimal place. The pseudo-positive month reflects the pseudo-positive minute. Middle case superior think filters into inferior middle case guess. The <<<^?”| upper space month hand and the <<<^?”\ upper time minute hand. The pseudo-positive old 19th decimal place. The pseudo-positive day reflects the pseudo-positive second. The somewhat superior think filters into inferior somewhat guess. The <<<^,?”| upper space day hand and the <<<^,?”\ upper time second hand.

The scientific annotated middle value hands, the front pseudo-positive dimensional hands.

The pseudo-positive old 18th decimal place. The clone pseudo-negative year filters into perpetual-pseudo positive year reflects the clone pseudo-negative hour filters into perpetual pseudo-positive hour. Clone superior think filters into perpetual inferior guess. The <<^“?”| middle space year hand and the <<^“?”\ middle time hour hand. The pseudo-positive old 17th decimal place. The pseudo-positive month reflects the pseudo-positive minute. Middle case superior think filters into inferior middle case guess. The <<^?”| middle space month hand and the <<^?”\ middle time minute hand. The pseudo-positive old 16th decimal place. The pseudo-positive day reflects the pseudo-positive second. The somewhat superior think filters into inferior somewhat guess. The <<^,?”| middle space day hand and the <<^,?”\ middle time second hand.

The scientific annotated inner value hands. The front pseudo-positive dimensional hands.

The pseudo-positive old 15th decimal place. The clone pseudo-negative year filters into perpetual-pseudo positive year reflects the clone pseudo-negative hour filters into perpetual pseudo-positive hour. Clone superior think filters into perpetual inferior guess. The <^“?”| inner space year hand and the <^“?”\ inner time hour hand. The pseudo-positive old 14th decimal place. The pseudo-positive month reflects the pseudo-positive minute. Middle case superior think filters into inferior middle case guess. The <^?”| inner space month hand and the <^?”\ inner time minute hand. The pseudo-positive old 13th decimal place. The pseudo-positive day reflects the pseudo-positive second. The somewhat superior think filters into inferior somewhat guess. The <^,?”| inner space day hand and the <^,?”\ inner time second hand.

The intelligent values.

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The behind thinking values.

The behind thinking annotated top value hands, the behind positive dimensional hands.

The positive old 24th decimal place. The clone negative year screens into perpetual positive year mirrors the clone negative hour screens into perpetual positive hour. Clone guess screens into perpetual think. The >>>>^“!| top space year hand and the >>>>^“!\ top time hour hand.

The positive old 23rd decimal place. The positive month mirrors the positive minute. Middle case guess screens into middle case think. The >>>>^!| top space month hand and the >>>>^!\ top time minute hand.

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The positive old 14th decimal place. The positive month mirrors the positive minute. Middle case guess screens into inferior middle case guess. The <^?!| inner space month hand and the <^?\ inner time minute hand.

The positive old 13th decimal place. The positive day mirrors the positive second. The somewhat guess screens into somewhat think. The <^,?!| inner space day hand and the <^,?! \ inner time second hand.

The annotation positive switch values.

The old positive 12th decimal place. Decline\$, switches to is actually \$saved.

The old positive 11th decimal place. Disintegration%, switches to is actually %regeneration.

The old positive 10th decimal place. Collapse}, switches to is actually {expand.

The old positive 9th decimal place. Disappear@, switches to is actually @appear.

The old positive 8th decimal place. Borrow&, switches to is actually &give.

The old positive 7th decimal place. Close*, switches to is actually *open.

The annotation positive values.

The old positive 6th decimal place.]Release[.

The old positive 5th decimal place.)Neither(.

The old positive 4th decimal place. ^Inflation.

The old positive 3rd decimal place. --Ever.

The old positive 2nd decimal place. +Capital.

The old positive 1st decimal place. 'Positive.

The superposition value.

The old positive 0th decimal place. -+Expiry.

The annotation negative values.

The old negative 1st decimal place. Negative,.

The old negative 2nd decimal place. Territory-.

The old negative 3rd decimal place. Never++.

The old negative 4th decimal place. Deflation^.

The old negative 5th decimal place. (Both).

The old negative 6th decimal place. [Seize].

The annotation negative switch values.

The old negative 7th decimal place. *open, switches to is actually closed*.

The old negative 8th decimal place. &give, switches to is actually borrow&.

The old negative 9th decimal place. @appear, switches to is actually disappear@.

The old negative 10th decimal place. {expand, switches to is actually collapse}

The old negative 11th decimal place. %regeneration, switches to is actually disintegration%.

The old negative 12th decimal place. \$saved, switches to is actually decline\$.

Note:

- There are the binary opposites to the thinking hands, and that is the guessing dimensional hands, the think that screens into a guess. There is also the pseudo-negative guessing hands, the superior guess that filters into a think, so it

effectively doesn't filter out all of the guess and becomes a gue-think. And so this can also be applied to the pseudo-positive superior think that filters into an inferior guess, which again effectively becomes a thin-guess as the filter doesn't filter out all of the think. With a guessing clock, it at least in most part is self explanatory, you have to guess about what value the dimensional hands are going to land on. The behind pseudo-negative values are, at least what I label them to be, is that of the quotient values, and the in-front pseudo-negative values, what I label as the genius values.

The annotations can also be applied to code, where also what is taken into consideration is that if writing a binary algorithm, always bold the first word of a sentence, as a bold word is a binary **1** and a word that is not in bold is a binary 0. An example of an algorithm using these annotations is this:

- **(IF** > gate > **#*THEN** > open > **#*THEN** > shared... > **then** > <<<<!>?\@&*).

If the finalists, last place finalists, and winners are on the left side of the positive values they are therefore on the right side of the positive values, however if they are on the right side of the positive values they are therefore on the left side of the positive values, and so the outcome is that they are on the right side of the positive values. And so if they are on the right side of the positive values they are therefore on the left side of the positive values, however if they are on the left side of the positive values they are on the right side of the positive values, and so the outcome of it is that they are on the left side of the positive values. And so the outcome of that absolute paradox is that the old positive locked values are either on the left side or right side of the positive values.

The value time travelling clock looks like so:

Note: there are no straight parts to this clock, it is all future moment, curved distance, acute angle, and rotation degree time based. The curved arrows are what the straight arrows look like from the side on.

The value space travelling clock looks like so:

Note: there are no curved parts to this clock. This clock is purely on position, forwards length, right area, and up volume space based.

The exponents.

0. 0.
1. 1.
2. 12.
3. 124.
4. 1248.
5. 12481.
6. 124816.
7. 1248163.
8. 12481632.
9. 124816326.
10. 1248163264.
11. 12481632641.
12. 124816326412.
13. 1248163264128.
14. 12481632641282.
15. 124816326412825.

16. 1248163264128256.
17. 12481632641282565.
18. 124816326412825651.
19. 1248163264128256512.
20. 12481632641282565121.
21. 124816326412825651210.
22. 1248163264128256512102.
23. 12481632641282565121024.
24. 124816326412825651210242.
25. 1248163264128256512102420.
26. 12481632641282565121024204.
27. 124816326412825651210242048.
28. 1248163264128256512102420484.
29. 12481632641282565121024204840.
30. 124816326412825651210242048409.
31. 1248163264128256512102420484096.
32. 12481632641282565121024204840968.
33. 124816326412825651210242048409681.
34. 1248163264128256512102420484096819.
35. , ,
36. . .

The exponent is applied onto the value hands and the annotated values. The exponents also are fluid, and so evolve depending on what is happening, if that is it is an old positive clock. If it is an old negative clock, the values may mis-evolve, not necessarily de-evolving, because when I at least hear the word with de- applied onto it, it leads me to the conclusion of degeneracy, and a guess isn't degenerate, it is merely a guess, because without my young positive guess when first coming up with this value chart, I wouldn't have been able to come up with it in the first place, as it is a model, and not necessarily research. There is also the notion of age transferency, where a young positive then transfers into an old negative. There is also the notion of a young value chart and an old value chart. What has been shown above is that of an old value chart. When a value chart is young, the old value chart gets reversed. So effectively a young positive becomes an old negative, and an young positive becomes an old negative. As these travelling clocks shown above are fluid, that is confined within the choice one makes about whether to use an old positive travelling clock, an old negative travelling clock, a young positive travelling clock, and a young negative travelling clock, there once again arises the notion of the shifting value, where a hand can figuratively pick up a value and carry the value to a higher or lower exponent, depending on what is happening. So eventually the value settles in place and again has more or less exponency applied onto that value.